

FARCLIMATE

DELIVERABLE 8.1 Initial communication and dissemination plan

Due date of submission: 31/03/2024

Actual submission date: 08/04/2024

Funded by
the European Union

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun Svizra
Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research ERFS
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

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Project information

Project full title: Moving ForwARd to achieving CLIMATE-resilient and sustainable European regional economic systems- FARCLIMATE

Acronym: FARCLIMATE

Call: HORIZON-MISS-2022-CLIMA-01

Topic: HORIZON-MISS-2022-CLIMA-01-04- Transformation of regional economic systems for climate resilience and sustainability

Start date: October 1st 2023

Duration: 48 months

List of participants:

Partner No.	Organization Name Acronym
1 (Coord.)	UNIVERSIDAD DE VIGO UVIGO
2	CONTACTICA S.L. CTA
3	INTERNATIONAL UNION FOR CONSERVATION OF NATURE UICN
4	C4G- CONSULTING AND TRAINING NETWORK, LDA C4G
5	INVIALBLE LIFE CYCLE THINKING S.L. INV
6	MUNICIPIO DO FUNDAO FUNDAO
7	GREEN GROWTH GENERATION GGG
8	UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE ULIEGE
9	FUNDACIÓN CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCIÓN FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEÓN CESEFOR
10	UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA UNL
11	FUNDACIÓN PARA LA PESCA Y MARISQUEO FUNDAMAR FUNDAMAR
12	European Network of Living Labs ENOLL
13	Centre for Research and Technology CERTH
14	Laurea University of Applied sciences LAUREA

Deliverable details

Document Number	D8.1
Document Title	Initial communication and dissemination plan
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Period	PR1
WP	WP8
Task	T8.1
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Abstract	<p>The FARCLIMATE project tackles the multifaceted challenges of fostering climate resilience across Europe by implementing innovative solutions. This communication plan outlines strategic initiatives aimed at disseminating project outcomes, collaboration, and empowering stakeholders to take informed action.</p> <p>Through targeted messaging, FARCLIMATE aims to engage key audiences, including the scientific community, policymakers, industry professionals, and the general public. The communication strategy encompasses various channels, including online platforms, social media, workshops, and conferences, to reach diverse audiences effectively. Key performance indicators (KPIs) such as website traffic, social media engagement, and workshop attendance will be monitored to evaluate the plan's effectiveness and inform ongoing optimization efforts.</p>

1 Introduction

This document corresponds to the deliverable D8.1- Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan.

The project FARCLIMATE will address the difficult challenges of developing and expanding climate-resilient measures across Europe. The project aims to make these measures accessible and comprehensible to diverse stakeholders, with a keen focus on addressing social, political, and economic barriers. Encompassing at least 20 regions and communities as case studies, FARCLIMATE sets out to implement transformative solutions within the agriculture, forestry, and fisheries sectors.

This Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan serves as a strategic guide for FARCLIMATE, outlining the comprehensive approach to engaging stakeholders, in close cooperation with T2.3. Stakeholder management strategy, and disseminating information. Our commitment extends to both responsible and affected stakeholders, including regional and local governments, the private sector, civil society, social partners, academia, and industries. By targeting these key players, FARCLIMATE ventures to foster collaboration, empower communities, and implement innovative solutions that enhance resilience to climate change impacts.

FARCLIMATE work program is structured around five key pillars:

- engaging with stakeholders
- establishing Living Labs for co-creation and testing
- conducting in-depth research on value chains and regional characteristics
- implementing transversal actions in case studies and employing nature-based solutions for resilience.
- These actions collectively aim to contribute to a climate-resilient future.

Innovative communication plays an important role in FARCLIMATE's strategy, emphasizing an inspirational approach that seeks to unite stakeholders towards a common goal of climate resilience. The project introduces a Transformation Hub, an online knowledge platform that incorporates narrative-driven visualization to enhance data understanding, thereby facilitating informed decision-making.

With a medium and long-term perspective, FARCLIMATE focuses on building resilience in various sectors and communities. Additionally, the project envisions extending its impact to create a future European Network dedicated to climate resilience. The consortium, comprising Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) partners, brings together expertise in environmental sciences, knowledge theory, business management, information technology, sustainability, agroecology, and communication, among others, ensuring the successful execution of FARCLIMATE's objectives.

In alignment with the EU strategy on adaptation to climate change, FARCLIMATE addresses key objectives such as making adaptation smarter, swifter, and more systemic, while also contributing to international efforts on climate change adaptation. The project recognizes the critical role of local and regional authorities, emphasizing the need for a collective and systemic approach to adaptation actions.

As a 48-month endeavor, FARCLIMATE adopts a twofold approach to achieve climate-change resilience in Europe. The project targets specific regions and communities while providing tools and recommendations for stakeholders often overlooked in traditional climate change communication. Key performance indicators will monitor the project's progress, aligning with the European Commission's strategy on adaptation to climate change.

This Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan serves as a foundation for FARCLIMATE's innovative and inclusive approach, emphasizing stakeholder engagement, co-creation, and the dissemination of valuable insights to shape a resilient and sustainable future for Europe.

2 Objectives

The communication objectives of the FARCLIMATE project are designed to align with its mission of fostering climate resilience across Europe through innovative and impactful communication strategies. The multifaceted nature of FARCLIMATE's goals needs a comprehensive and forward-thinking approach to disseminate information effectively, engage stakeholders, and inspire collective action.

Depending on the target audience that FARCLIMATE wants to address and the nature of the project's information and content, there will be two approaches:

- **Communication:** it involves everything related to the project, news about all sectors participating in FARCLIMATE and any piece of information that doesn't contain specific non-public data. Disclosure of some data or information about the project and its work packages is desirable in order to show transparency and expand knowledge, but for scientific and technical data, the dissemination tools are available. The main objective of the project communication is for any piece of information to spread as much as possible and to make the project known for as many people as possible.

Also, FARCLIMATE wants to become a reliable source of curated and informative content about the development of climate-resilient measures across Europe. This means that, in order to be perceived as such, news and content created by others about these topics will be spread through all project channels. And, also, informative content produced in different ways (visual materials, information pieces, etc) will be posted periodically in order to increase FARCLIMATE's community and reinforce this image of a reliable source of sustainability information.

- **Dissemination:** the dissemination of the project involves the public disclosure of project-generated results. It is normally addressed to: researchers, academia, researchers, professionals of different sectors, stakeholders, etc. However, dissemination actions can also target other specific audiences, such as science weeks for students and general public, who may be interested in FARCLIMATE's results and progress. Open access in scientific publications will be actively pursued, so any audience can download these results from any specific audience.

With this in mind, the following communication and dissemination objectives outline the strategic focus areas for achieving success:

2.1 Communication Objectives:

1. **To raise awareness about the project's objectives by developing a narrative approach.** To convey the project outcomes and insights and counteract the challenges associated with the complexities of climate science communication, the information will be presented in a compelling, relatable, and positive manner.
2. **To encourage a proactive stance toward climate change mitigation and adaptation.** Addressing the psychological aspect of climate change communication by fostering positive responses will ultimately drive support for sustainable practices and resilience-building efforts.
3. **To involve and engage stakeholders throughout the project, incorporating their ideas, suggestions, and perspectives.** Establishing a collaborative approach by tapping into the expertise and insights of various stakeholders, ensuring their active participation in decision-making processes and promoting knowledge sharing.
4. **To implement innovative communication platforms, including the Transformation Hub (digital platform) and other channels,** to effectively reach diverse audiences. Leveraging digital tools and strategic platforms will maximize the reach of communication outputs, ensuring accessibility, engagement, and relevance to different stakeholders.

5. To share successful results, key learnings, and identified barriers regarding climate change adaptation through various communication tools such as policy recommendations, guidelines, and management plans. This enables stakeholders to replicate successful approaches and adapt strategies to their unique circumstances.

2.2 Dissemination Objectives:

1. To disseminate specialized knowledge gained from FARCLIMATE to specific target audiences, such as policymakers, industry leaders, and academic institutions. This information will be generated to meet the unique needs and interests of key stakeholders, facilitating a more focused and effective transfer of project insights.
2. To document and share best practices identified during the project across diverse sectors, including agriculture, forestry, and fisheries. Establishing a comprehensive repository of successful strategies and approaches that can be easily accessed and implemented by stakeholders in similar contexts. This objective aims to provide tangible solutions and guidance based on real-world experiences within the scope of FARCLIMATE.
3. To organise interactive workshops and sessions to facilitate knowledge exchange between different stakeholders involved in climate resilience efforts. The interactive nature of these workshops promotes active engagement and fosters a collaborative learning environment.
4. To maximize the utilization of the Transformation Hub (digital platform) for widespread dissemination of project outcomes, guidelines, and recommendations. Leverage the digital platform to reach a broad audience, providing easily accessible resources and fostering ongoing engagement. The Transformation Hub will serve as a central hub for sharing information, enabling stakeholders to stay informed and connected.
5. To implement Living Labs as localized dissemination hubs, conducting on-site events and co-creation processes tailored to specific regions and communities. Recognizing the importance of localized engagement by customizing dissemination efforts to address unique challenges and opportunities within the different local contexts. Living Labs serve as focal points for targeted, community-specific knowledge dissemination.

3 Target audiences and key messages

The first thing to take into account is the audience that FARCLIMATE project will be addressing its materials and messages to. Different audiences need different messages presented in different channels, so it is key to identify them in the first place. The following criteria guide the selection of target audiences:

- Interest in the project topics, knowledge shared and development of the different working lines.
- Ability to share any information piece FARCLIMATE produces.
- Involvement in the project.
- Influence over the project and/or the rest of target audiences.
- Ability to maximize any communication and dissemination action.
- Capacity to create synergies and networking.
- Interest in the potential advances of FARCLIMATE to the bio-based industries.
- Potential beneficiaries of FARCLIMATE's advances.
- Other interested audiences.

Following these criteria and the communication and dissemination objectives five different groups have been individuated:

Table 1. Audience target groups for FARCLIMATE

Audience	Objectives	Actions
Scientific and innovation community	Share knowledge with researchers and foster networking and collaboration.	Prepare publications, participate in events, disseminate findings through standard research channels.
European Commission and other EU platforms	Demonstrate the effective use of EU resources, share knowledge, and network with relevant stakeholders.	Manage project activities, participate in EU events, share project results.
Responsible authorities	Increase awareness about policymaking for sectoral resilience.	Present FARCLIMATE recommendations and guidelines, attend relevant events, share project contributions.
Private sector, professionals and expert	Increase awareness about sector-specific challenges and potential measures for climate adaptation.	Disseminate materials, participate in events, share FARCLIMATE case studies, conduct workshops and webinars.
Living lab community	Increase awareness about participatory approaches to addressing societal and environmental issues, impact as many people as possible.	Disseminate materials, facilitate workshops and events, organize webinars and online events.
General public	Educate the public about climate change challenges and potential solutions, empower individuals to take action.	Develop accessible communication materials, conduct public awareness campaigns, organize outreach events, disseminate information through mainstream and social media platforms.

Once the audience has been identified, it is key to search for tailor-made messages. With so many different audiences to reach, it is important to distribute the project's core values among different messages and communicate them through different channels with specific communicative goals.

These messages must reflect:

- Main values of the project
- The project's evolution
- The project's goals
- The project's results and impact
- FARCLIMATE'S contributions to the SDGs, specially: 13) Climate action, 11) Sustainable Cities and Communities, 15) Life on Land, by providing Nature-based Solutions (NbS), 8) Decent work and economic growth via considering all stakeholders during the implementation of solutions, 4) Quality education, 9) Industry, innovation and infrastructure.

These are the selected basic messages for the FARCLIMATE communication strategy and each target audience:

Table 2. Messages for audience target groups for FARCLIMATE

For the general public
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase awareness about the impacts of climate change on daily lives and communities. • Educate individuals about practical measures they can take to adapt to climate change and contribute to resilience efforts. • Inspire action and collective engagement towards building a climate-resilient future for all.
For the Living lab community
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn about the best practices and co-creation activities implemented in the 20 case studies involved in FARCLIMATE's Living Labs.

- Understand the benefits derived from the knowledge exchange and collaboration within the Living Lab community.
- Participate in dissemination activities, workshops, and events to increase awareness and impact societal and environmental issues in local communities.

For the private sector, professionals and expert

- Discover the business opportunities and benefits associated with adapting to climate change in the fishery, agriculture, and forestry sectors.
- Explore evidence-based solutions and best practices tailored to meet industry needs and challenges posed by climate change.
- Participate in workshops and webinars to gain insights from FARCLIMATE's case studies and collaborate with experts from academia and research institutions.

For the responsible authorities

- Understand the specific challenges faced by workers in the fishery, forestry, and agricultural sectors due to climate change.
- Recognize the urgent need to adapt these sectors to climate change and the potential benefits of resilience-building measures.
- Access recommendations and guidelines from FARCLIMATE to inform policymaking and regulatory actions aimed at enhancing sectoral resilience.

For the European Commission and other EU platforms

- Gain insights into the process and results of the FARCLIMATE project to support evidence-based decision-making.
- Extract valuable knowledge and learnings from FARCLIMATE for application in other EU-funded projects and initiatives.
- Engage in networking opportunities to strengthen collaborations and synergies between FARCLIMATE and other relevant EU initiatives.

For the scientific and innovation community

- Access comprehensive data on sector-specific climate change challenges to inform research and innovation efforts.
- Explore potential feasible measures for climate adaptation based on evidence-based findings from FARCLIMATE.
- Collaborate with peers and experts to foster networking and knowledge exchange in the field of climate resilience.

In addition, **keywords are helpful in our communication strategy in various contexts.** In academic and professional writing, keywords help convey the main themes and topics of a document. Including appropriate keywords makes it easier for readers, researchers, or stakeholders to quickly understand the key concepts and find information relevant to their interests.

When creating content for FARCLIMATE's channels, keywords guide content creation by providing a focus so the consortium can ensure that their material aligns with what users are searching for. This improves the chances of the content being discovered by the target audience. And also, on social media platforms, the use of relevant keywords can enhance the visibility of posts. Users often search for content using keywords or hashtags, and incorporating these effectively can increase the reach of social media posts.

These are some of the main FARCLIMATE's keywords:

- Climate resilience
- Adaptation

- Sustainability
- Innovation
- Community engagement
- Climate challenges
- Sector-specific solutions
- Knowledge exchange
- Stakeholder collaboration
- Environmental impact
- Climate-resilient measures
- Transformative solutions
- Stakeholder engagement
- Living Labs
- Socioeconomic analysis
- Value chains
- Community empowerment
- Nature-based solutions
- Policy recommendations
- Innovation Hub

4 Channels and strategy

To address the targeted audiences with the proper messages, dedicated channels are needed, as well as specific actions throughout the duration of the project. In this chart some of the main communication and dissemination channels and actions are displayed:

Table 3. Communication channels for FARCLIMATE

CHANNEL	WHAT
Website http://farclimate-project.eu/	Information and news about the project, its progress and results; project articles and own project events (or with FARCLIMATE presence).
Twitter https://twitter.com/farclimate_he	Information and news about the project, its progress and results; articles related to the FARCLIMATE subject; factsheets and infographics; projects and websites of interest to the stakeholders.
LinkedIn https://www.linkedin.com/company/farclimate-project	Information regarding the project and its development and results: consortium meetings; results; presence at external events, informative content.
Communication materials	Newsletters, brochures, factsheets, infographics. Designed during all the project to raise awareness on important facts, data and/or project progress.
Communication campaigns	Sending press releases about the project and promoting the project in mass media is vital to achieve the maximum visibility. Also, online campaigns in social media are key to reinforce FARCLIMATE's online presence.
Scientific publications	Published in open access to spread technical knowledge about the most specialized audiences.
Workshops and trainings	Organised or co-organised by project partners and inviting experts on specific fields.
Events	Conferences, round table discussions, EU events, networking... These tools may raise awareness of the project and also enrich it.
Partners' existing channels	Partners' websites, social media accounts or platforms can help promote the project activity.

4.1 Project's website

FARCLIMATE project website (<http://farclimate-project.eu/>) was designed as a visual and user-friendly channel to showcase the project's brand and to provide non-confidential project information. The navigation through the site is easy and the language used for many of the articles should remain comprehensible and casual to attract as many people from general public as possible. Pieces of information such as project context, core objectives, project structure, impacts and expected outcomes, partners, links to news and events, and informative content will be shared periodically on the website. A private area for partners has been designed in order to ensure an efficient internal communication and store information and deliverables.

4.2 Social Media

Social media are a key part of the communication plan. On the one hand, they are the brand and image of the project towards people who don't participate in the project. On the other hand, they are the main communication window to reach general public as well as other stakeholders and targeted audiences. They are also useful to:

- Redirect traffic to the FARCLIMATE website and to raise visitors and page views.
- Create a coherent brand for the project.
- Spread all contents, events, project activities.
- Serve as the visual channel for the project.

FARCLIMATE will use Twitter and LinkedIn, unless a different agreement is set or other social networks are proposed. If other channels prove beneficial for the projects' objectives, they will be created.

In terms of users, as they are slightly predominantly male-user social networks (The Global State of Digital 2022, Hootsuite) so there is gender disparity present in these social networks. In order to mitigate this issue, and based on the project statistics and the guidelines established in T1.5 Gender Transformative Programming, other channels will be considered.

Also, there is an age bias, as a high percentage of many social media users are aged 24-34 years old average, with changes from one channel to another (The Global State of Digital 2022, Hootsuite). The communication of the project will take these facts into account and will pursue other ways to be able to communicate with all possible audiences, regardless their age or gender, such as the mentioned science weeks or meetings and workshops designed for younger audiences.

Networking and joint actions will be performed with other sister EU funded projects through social media in order to grow all projects' visibility and generate more impact. Also, the help of the partners' channels is key to maximize the visibility of FARCLIMATE in each and every step of the project.

4.3 Communication materials

Communication materials will be designed during the project lifetime to be used by partners when necessary and sometimes to be used as engagement tools for targeted audiences. CTA, as leader of WP8 is responsible for the creation of all communication material, but all partners are allowed to produce their own, always respecting the branding, visual identity and core project values, and always informing CTA.

The main communication materials are:

- **Brochure:** for general communication of the project targets and showing the main objectives, expected outcomes, partners and regions involved.
- **Posters:** to increase visibility of both the project and its partners.
- **Audio-visual and graphic materials:** to help the comprehension of the project.
- **PowerPoint presentation:** updated regularly. It should be used in conferences and external events where partners are participating and should help them explain the project and how it is developing.

- **Roll-up:** for general communication of the project targets and showing the main objectives, expected outcomes, partners and regions involved.
- **Videos:** explanatory videos will be made, showing the achievements of the project and lessons learnt. The target audience will be end-users and policymakers. The video will be promoted via social media and events (e.g., workshops).

When possible, the communication materials and documents will be adapted in terms of accessibility to be read by voice assistants. This will be pursued by titles and sections in documents, in order to be user friendly for these kind of voice assistants, as well as in social media.

4.4 Online communication campaigns

With the main aim of attracting and establishing FARCLIMATE's community around our stakeholders and the general public, an online communication strategy has been established with three main pillars:

- The FARCLIMATE website will be permanently updated through the section of news and events.
- Social media and newsletters will be used to share the advances about the project included in the website, and attract visitors and users. Specific calls to action will be published in order to measure engagement and to achieve all communication objectives.
- Search Engine Optimization (SEO) techniques will be used to obtain a good positioning of the website on Internet browsers.

4.5 Scientific publications

It is expected that the project develops several results from some of the work packages and they will be addressed to different key scientific communities. The publications will be made freely and openly available via an online repository. Prior to publishing any scientific publication, the FARCLIMATE partner involved will contact the whole consortium for revision and validation of the publication 45 days in advance. More information for this is presented in **Section 7. Dissemination: Open Access**.

4.6 Workshops

These sessions will be organized with local stakeholders and different targeted audiences depending on the specific topic. As the project evolves, different workshops and actions will be organized with various groups of interesting audiences. Different lines have been identified in order to organise workshops:

- Different lines have been identified in order to organise workshops:
- Initial engagement with relevant stakeholders in each region.
- Establishment of Living Labs for co-creation, testing, and scaling-up innovative activities.
- Research on the main value chains, socioeconomic, and environmental characteristics of investigated regions.
- Tailor-made training activities for community empowerment.
- Implementation of technically and socially feasible innovative solutions in agriculture, forestry, and fisheries sectors.

4.7 Events

Events are one of the most important parts of the dissemination and communication strategy because they allow the project members and the project to connect with stakeholders and the general public, encourage networking and show the most important advances and results of the project. Events also feed of content the communication channels and tools (website, social media, press releases) generating great impacts on different audiences. They can be in-person events, hybrid, webinars, conferences or other kinds of happenings that the consortium considers.

The participation of partners in events will be made visible through the FARCLIMATE website and social media channels contributing to increasing the community of stakeholders and public interested in the project.

General and technical presentations of FARCLIMATE will be showcased in face-to-face interactions with stakeholders when possible. CTA will actively look for events, conferences and opportunities for all members to attend in order to network, enrich the project and spread knowledge about it but, if any member finds interesting events to attend to, it would be useful to communicate it beforehand, so CTA can promote it in all dedicated channels. Specific actions and joint activities will be organized with sister projects. This can enable synergies as well as spread the project messages further and generate more visibility for the project’s channels.

4.8 Clustering and networking

FARCLIMATE Consortium will join forces with other Horizon projects and our participation in Nature-based Solutions Task Forces, such as NetworkNature. By aligning our strategies and collaborating with relevant initiatives, we aim to maximize impact and foster synergies in advancing our goals.

Some of these sister projects have already been identified:

Table 4. Sister projects identified for FARCLIMATE

Project name	Topic	End date
SoilDiverAgro	The EU-funded SoildiverAgro project aims to propose new practices increasing quality and production of crops while reducing external inputs.	May-2025
CARDIMED	CARDIMED project aims to establish a framework and network for enhancing climate resilience in the Mediterranean biogeographical region, bringing together disparate efforts and solutions.	Feb-2028
DesirMED	DesirMED will increase ambition, ownership and capability of regional Med leaders and communities through proven transformative Climate Change Adaptation approaches	Dec-28
Natalie	NATALIE addresses the risks posed by climate change and its impacts and proposes to advance the concepts of “ecosystem-based adaptation” in Europe combined with climate resilient development pathways.	Aug-2028

5 Management of Communication and Dissemination

CTA is the leader of the WP8 and coordinates the actions and processes with the inputs of the rest of the members of the consortium. Additionally, some specific procedures will be designed to organize, in an effective way, the external communication, the generation of content in the website, the social media work, the review of communication and dissemination materials, and the information and reporting about the participation in events.

It is also CTA’s duty to collect all project communication impacts, readjust the communication plan when needed and report to the rest of the consortium. This task, though, is also a collaborative one and all project members are requested to share information of interest to CTA.

5.1 Website

CTA is responsible for the management of the website and will update regularly (at least once a month) the FARCLIMATE website with news and events. CTA will request information from the partners to prepare the news.

The events to which FARCLIMATE’s partners are attending to have to be promoted through the website and also from social media. To do it so, partners need to inform CTA beforehand so news can be published. Members of the consortium are requested to promote press releases, offer information to create posts on the

website, and other content and materials through their own communication tools and channels: website, social media profiles, newsletters, etc. And they are also requested, to provide CTA with photos to upload in every information piece of the website. For the follow-up of the website, analytic tools will be used. These tools will give information regarding the number of visitors, countries, type of business and so on. Reports will be prepared and analysed yearly with the consortium.

And they are requested, too, to provide CTA with photos to upload in every information piece of the website. For the follow-up of the website, analytic tools will be used. These tools will give information regarding the number of visitors, countries, type of business and so on. Reports will be prepared and analysed yearly with the consortium.

5.2 Social media channels

CTA will mainly manage the social media accounts, but all partners can prepare and send information to CTA in order to share interesting information and posts. All contents will be published in English. However, retweets can come from tweets in other languages.

All partners should follow FARCLIMATE social media accounts with their personal/institutional accounts and they should share the project social media accounts with their contacts to create an online network through different platforms. FARCLIMATE website links to the social media accounts as well as the social media accounts link to the website.

5.2.1 Twitter

Twitter is the most popular micro-blogging site and represents the opportunity to reach people from all over the world with interests related to the project. It is also a requirement from the EU, as all funded projects have a Twitter account.

In addition, it is a good opportunity to create a knowledge network, as all EU institutions and other groups of interest and stakeholders also own Twitter accounts. CTA is responsible for the management of the Twitter account of the project. Partners must collaborate by mentioning the FARCLIMATE accounts, retweeting the messages about the project and sharing publications.

On Twitter, third parties' content can be shared if it might result interesting to followers, as it can attract these third parties to follow the account, raise engagement and give image of a strong and reliable curated content source, as stated before. It can be done through retweets or by giving credit to the owner (expressed by the formula "via @name of the original publisher"). Use of #hashtags and @mentions is highly recommended to increase the impact of the tweet. The language will be clear, but technical or scientific terms can be used if needed.

These hashtags have been created or considered relevant for FARCLIMATE in Twitter: [#FARCLIMATE](#) [#FARCLIMATEProject](#) [#HorizonEU](#) [#ClimateResilience](#) [@cinea_eu](#)

5.2.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the most popular networking online site. It is used for connecting with people that work in similar or related fields, as well as sharing knowledge. CTA is responsible of the management of this channel, but any partner can be included as administrator of the page in order to upload information. Partners are free to ask for this access to CTA.

LinkedIn should be updated regularly, with at least 1 post every week. Posts that include multimedia elements are highly recommended. The language will be clear, but technical or scientific terms can be used if necessary. This network can help the project reach a lot of interesting stakeholders from the different professional areas and to generate engagement and a good visibility for the project.

5.2.3 YouTube

This social media channel is the most visited video network, with millions of visitors. We are considering opening up this network and upload project videos as well as videos of project members talking about their organization and work. As the topics addressed in the project can be hard to understand for the general public, we can ease this task through easy and short project videos.

This network will be updated regularly, or whenever the consortium members deliver content to CTA. All members can send videos or information to CTA. The content will be uploaded in English, but some content may be displayed in the other languages of the project members.

5.3 Communication materials

CTA is in charge of developing communication materials to promote the project. Partners must inform with enough time in advance if they need some of these materials for events participation or other requirements.

Press releases are and will be produced and sent to several interested parties to network with throughout the project. It will be uploaded to the website, where it can be downloaded, and translated into the consortium languages. The project brochure has been designed and it will be printed and taken to any event or activity involving the project for its promotion and visibility. Posters, factsheets, videos and other communication materials will be developed during the project.

5.4 Communication campaigns

In some moments of the project, it is important to communicate FARCLIMATE findings, evolution or milestones with a special emphasis. That is when communication campaigns are necessary to spread the message further. These campaigns may include:

- Press releases.
- Publications in online and printed media.
- Special social media campaigns.
- Promotion of events and workshops.

These campaigns will be carried out in specific moments of the project and will require specific tools and strategies to succeed and reach as many people as possible or achieve specific campaign goals.

5.5 Reporting events

Partners of the consortium will attend to relevant events, conferences and workshops. They should be actively involved in seeking opportunities to present and showcase the project in their own countries and at a European level. The participation in events must be previously communicated to CTA (to make visible activities through communication channels), and after the event, every partner must report about the activity: sum-up, number of attendees, pictures, publications, presentations, press clipping, etc.

If results are going to be shared in an event, partners need to inform or ask permission from the Exploitation Board to do so before the event.

5.6 Support from the European Commission

The support to the FARCLIMATE project by the European Union must be recognised in all the dissemination and communication tools and materials. Any communication and dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- a) display the EU flag and the text Funded by the European Union. You can download them [here](#).

b) include the following text: *Funded by the European Union under grant agreement 101112860. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.*

6 Evaluation process: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

CTA coordinates the Communication and Dissemination Plan and its activities with the involvement of all the members of the consortium. Each partner will make use of its communication tools and channels, networks and collaboration to reach the stakeholders of the project and build the FARCLIMATE community.

CTA compiles all the information about the events attended, upcoming events, other networking and collaborative activities, as well as the impacts on media. These are the minimum KPI for the project:

Table 5. Key performance indicators for FARCLIMATE

Activity	Indicators	Target
Website	# of visits	6000
	# of visitors	1000
Social media	# of Followers	Twitter 200 LinkedIn 250
	# of newsletters	8
Newsletter	# of subscribers	100
	# downloads	250
	Press releases	# of documents
Videos	# of visualizations of the video-documentaries	300 per video
Brochure	# of project brochures handed and downloaded	500 1000
	Scientific publications	# of publications
Workshops	# of workshops organised	8
Conferences	# of presentations/ attendance	12
Clustering activities	# of clustering activities	10
	# contact public bodies	10

7 Dissemination: Open Access

Open access (OA) refers to the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and reusable. 'Scientific' refers to all academic disciplines. In the context of research and innovation, 'scientific information' can mean:

- Peer-reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals).
- Research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).

7.1 Peer-reviewed scientific research articles

Open access to scientific publications means free online access for any user. Although there are no legally binding definitions of 'access' or 'open access' in this context, authoritative definitions of open access appear in key political declarations including:

- the 2002 [Budapest Declaration](#)

- the 2003 [Berlin Declaration](#)

Under these definitions, 'access' includes not only basic elements- the right to read, download and print – but also **the right to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl and mine**.

The 2 main routes to open access are:

- **Self-archiving / 'green' open access** – the author, or a representative, archives (deposits) the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository before, at the same time as, or after publication.
- **Open access publishing / 'gold' open access** - an article is immediately published in open access mode.

There are two ways to ensure immediate open access:

1. Deposit your publication in a repository for scientific publications and ensure open access.
2. Publish your research in an open access journal.

In both cases you have to deposit your publications in a repository, even when publishing in an open access journal.

In the context of research funding, **open access requirements do not imply an obligation to publish results**. The decision to publish is entirely up to the grant beneficiaries. **Open access becomes an issue *only if* publication is chosen as a means of dissemination**.

Moreover, open access does not affect the decision to exploit research results commercially, e.g. through patenting. The decision on whether to publish through open access must come after the more general decision on whether to publish directly or to first seek protection.

7.1.1 Mandate on open access to publications

The open-access mandate comprises 2 steps: (1) depositing publications in repositories, (2) providing open access to them. The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

7.2 Open access to research data

Open access to **research data** refers to the right to access and reuse digital research data under the terms and conditions set out in the Grant Agreement. Research data refers to **information**, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. **The focus is on research data that is available in digital form**. Users can normally access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate openly accessible research data free of charge.

FARCLIMATE will use OpenAIRE's **Zenodo platform as the primary choice for depositing open data**. Zenodo¹ is a popular repository for making Horizon Europe projects data and publications open and provides easy functionalities for making them FAIR.

Additionally, other trusted repositories could also be used. In this sense, repositories endorsed by the research communities in the fields of the data or publication are also recommended. *OpenAire Explore*² and *Open Research Europe-approved repositories*³ are useful sources for identifying trusted repositories.

Annex I - Visual identity manual

¹ <https://zenodo.org>

² <https://explore.openaire.eu/search/content-providers>

³ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/data-guidelines#approvedrepositories>

Visual Identity Manual

FARCLIMATE

Introduction

This manual includes the visual elements representing the corporate identity of FARCLIMATE. Conveying a consistent and controlled message of who we are is essential to present a strong and unified image of FARCLIMATE.

This manual collects all foreseeable visualizations of the logo and establishes guidelines regulating their applications in a simple and coherent manner.

Corporate identity helps reaffirm the company or entity and creates a clear image, enhancing the organization's communications.

The goal is to gather the elements that shape this identity and lay the groundwork for its use in current and/or future applications, aiming to be a guiding reference tool regarding graphic standards across various media and platforms.

Elements not defined in this manual will be developed in line with the general criteria and style set forth here. Proper application in cases not covered will depend on the judgment of the Communication and Corporate Image Area of the organization to achieve optimal legibility and visual identity.

Description

FARCLIMATE will tackle the complex challenges of developing and expanding measures that promote resilience to climate change, intending to make them accessible and understandable to all, paying special attention to the social, political, and economic barriers often encountered in at least 20 regions and communities in Europe, which will serve as case studies. FARCLIMATE will implement actions focused on transformative solutions to advance climate resilience. This project is aimed at both responsible actors and those affected, including regional and local governments, the private sector, civil society, social collaborators, academic institutions, industries, and others, focusing on three key sectors affected by climate change: **agriculture, forestry, and fisheries.**

Our Logo

Logo Variations

Logo Icons

Typography

A B C D E F G H
I J K L M N Ñ O
P Q R S T U V
W X Y Z

Bourton Hand Base

Typography plays a significant role in communication. Careful use of typography reinforces personality, ensuring clarity and harmony in all communications. Bourton Hand Base has been selected.

Color Palette

Primary Color:
#003C40

100%

80%

60%

40%

20%

Color Palette

Secondary Color:
#00A975

100%

80%

60%

40%

20%

Color Palette

Contrast Color:
#FF7700

100%

80%

60%

40%

20%

Applications

Fecha
Titulo
Dirección nombre de la calle,
Ciudad, País, CP 012345

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